

A Pilot Study: Effects of an 8-week training intervention in carbon-plated running shoes

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Abstract

Lab testing with Nike Vaporflys (VP) has revealed running economy (RE) benefits of 2.5-4%. With runners also anecdotally reporting less sore calf muscles and less “beat up” legs after hard workouts, use of these shoes may cause runners to undergo physiological adaptations since their muscles may be aided during training by the shoe’s energy returning technology. The purpose of this pilot study is to investigate the long-term effects of using VP in workouts by comparing training in VP vs traditional racing flats (FL) on race performance and explore physiological and biomechanical adaptations.

Collegiate cross-country runners (n=8) completed pre- and post-intervention testing in both VP and FL. They were assigned either VP or FL for an 8-week intervention. Metabolic and biomechanical data were collected and compared.

FL-trained runners improved average running economy more than the VP-trained runners (FL: $5.61 \pm 1.11\%$; VP: $0.97 \pm 3.64\%$; $p=0.077$, ES (g)=1.409). Computing a “VP % benefit” by comparing the RE when running in VP compared to running in FL, the VP-trained runners increased VP % Benefit compared to FL-trained runners (VP: $0.21 \pm 2.23\%$; FL: $-0.38 \pm 0.24\%$; $p=0.433$, $g=0.148$). In this pilot phase there were no significant correlations between biomechanical and metabolic measures. Heterogeneity of foot strike techniques likely prevented group biomechanical differences from being observed. We will use the effect sizes of these differences to power the next larger phase of the study.

This pilot study suggests a specificity of training effect where participants improved relative RE more from PRE to POST when running in the shoe type they trained in. Overall, the FL group improved RE to a greater extent, suggesting that training in FL is more optimal for race performance despite decreasing the acute RE benefits incurred from super shoes.

Key Words: Running, Footwear, Biomechanics, Physiology, Performance, Gait

1. Introduction

Since the introduction of the Nike ZoomX Vaporfly 4% in 2016 and the public release of the shoe to customers in 2017, the distance running world has become a blur. With men’s and women’s world records falling on the roads and track from 5km to marathon (Muniz-Pardos et al. 2021) after the introduction of these shoes, most running shoe companies rushed to create their own “super shoe”. These shoes employ the use of a carbon fiber plate, or one made of a similarly stiff material, and ample lightweight, bouncy foam. Heel stack heights are now typically around 40mm, including the Nike Vaporfly Next% 2 (VP), which weighs 196 grams and is the super shoe model used in this pilot study (Figure 1a). Prior to the introduction of polyether block amide (PEBA) foam and widespread carbon-fiber use in racing footwear, traditional racing flats prioritized minimizing weight with a lower stack height and typically did not include full-length plate to increase longitudinal bending stiffness. The traditional racing flat used in this pilot study, the Nike Zoom

Victory Waffle 5 (FL), has a 17mm heel stack height and weighs 131 grams (Figure 1b). The acute biomechanical and physiological effects of super shoes compared to traditional racing flats are becoming well documented (Hoogkamer et al. 2018, 2019; Castellanos-Salamanca et al. 2023; Hunter et al. 2019, 2022; Nigg et al. 2020; Joubert and Jones 2022). The performance advantage of super shoes are typically quantified through measuring differences in running economy (RE), which is the amount of oxygen used to run at a submaximal velocity (VO_2 ; $\text{ml}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) (Barnes and Kilding 2015). Lab testing with Nike Vaporflys (VP) has revealed running economy improvements of 2.5-4% (Hoogkamer et al. 2018; Joubert and Jones 2022), accompanied by decreased metatarsophalangeal joint (MTP) work and a shortened moment arm between the ground reaction force and the ankle joint. (Hoogkamer et al. 2019; Farina et al. 2019) With runners reporting less muscular pain (Castellanos-Salamanca et al. 2023) and less “beat up” legs after hard workouts, use of VP may cause runners to undergo physiological adaptations since their muscles are aided during training by the shoe’s energy returning technology.

Fig. 1a. Nike Vaporfly Next% 2 (VP)

Fig. 1b. Nike Zoom Victory Waffle 5 racing flat (FL)

With the increased prevalence of VP being used for workouts as well as races, we aim to investigate the potential long-term benefits or drawbacks of using VP regularly in workouts by comparing the effects of training in VP to training in FL on performance and to explore potential physiological and biomechanical adaptations that may explain these effects. Specifically, we hypothesize that eight weeks of training for both groups will improve RE, plantarflexor strength in both positions measured, and vertical jump height. Furthermore, we hypothesize that FL-trained runners will improve to a greater extent in the previously mentioned outcome measures compared to VP-trained runners. Additionally, we predict that FL-trained runners will increase their acute VP performance benefit due to increases in plantarflexor strength while VP-trained runners will decrease their acute performance benefits from VP.

2. Methods

2.1 Participants

Nine collegiate cross-country runners (age: 20 ± 2.29 years; height: 175.0 ± 7.03 cm; body mass: 62.21 ± 7.96 kg) were recruited from the men’s and women’s NCAA Division 2 cross country teams at California State University East Bay. More detailed demographic info for the eight runners who completed the study is shown in Table 1. Participants were eligible if they were participating in an organized university cross country team, at least 18 years of age, and must have completed their previous competitive season and summer training without injury that resulted in more than two weeks of rest from regular training. Exclusion criteria included any lower extremity musculoskeletal problem that required more than two weeks rest from running in the last three months, or any serious injury or surgery on the lower extremities. All participants provided informed consent to participate, all procedures were approved by the Institutional Review Board.

Participants completed identical pre- (PRE) and post- (POST) intervention lab testing in both VP and FL and trained in either VP or FL shoes for eight weeks in between these testing sessions. During PRE, participants gave informed consent; completed a Running Questionnaire (Nielsen et al. 2019) that captured details about training status, load, injury history, running shoe preference,

and previous workout/racing shoes worn; and shoes were fitted. In PRE and POST, participant height and weight were recorded.

	FL Training Group (Mean \pm SD)	VP Training Group (Mean \pm SD)
n	2	6
Male/Female	1/1	5/1
Age (years)	22.0 \pm 1.41	19.67 \pm 2.34
Height (cm)	175.0 \pm 8.49	175.33 \pm 7.99
Weight (kg)	59.75 \pm 7.14	64.70 \pm 9.68
Self-Selected Race Pace (km \cdot hr ⁻¹)	18.06 \pm 0.81	18.27 \pm 0.79
Self-Selected Submaximal Pace (km \cdot hr ⁻¹)	16.04 \pm 0.88	16.44 \pm 0.78
Self-Selected Race Pace (MM:SS per mile)	05:20 \pm 00:23	5:17 \pm 00:21
Self-Selected Submaximal Pace (MM:SS per mile)	06:01 \pm 00:32	5:52 \pm 00:27
Weekly Mileage (miles)	66.04 \pm 3.47	58.10 \pm 6.95
Weekly Workout Mileage (miles)	20.17 \pm 1.77	21.72 \pm 1.01
Adherence to Shoe Type	87.50 \pm 12.50%	93.80 \pm 3.95%

Table 1. Participant characteristics within each shoe group (FL & VP).

2.2 Instrumentation

Participants were instrumented with a 6DoF retroreflective lower-body marker set and ran on a force plate instrumented treadmill (1000Hz, Treadmetrix, Park City, UT, USA). Additional foot markers were used to distinguish a toe segment between the MTP joints and the distal phalanx of the first digit from a foot segment between the MTP joints and the calcaneus (Jarvis and Kulig 2016). All markers were placed by the same individual who was trained in marker placement, with a second trained individual ensuring proper placement. Motion data were captured with an 8-camera Vicon Nexus System (Vicon Motion Systems LTD, United Kingdom).

2.3 Procedures

Prior to treadmill testing, functional measures of vertical jump (VJ) and plantarflexor strength were acquired. VJ was measured with a countermovement jump (Vertec, Sports Imports, Worthington, OH, USA). After recording reach height, participants were instructed on how to complete a countermovement jump and were given two practice jumps for familiarization (Buckthorpe et al. 2012). Three jumps were measured with the height of the highest two jumps averaged and recorded (Leard et al. 2007; Yingling et al. 2018). Plantarflexor strength was measured in two positions with a handheld dynamometer (microFET®2 Digital Handheld Dynamometer, Hoggan Scientific, Salt Lake City, Utah, USA) and subjects were instructed to generate maximal force for about 5 seconds (Liebl et al. 2014). In the first position (knee flexed), participants were seated with 90 degrees of knee and hip flexion, their thigh was secured, and the microFET was positioned under the forefoot, specifically the 2nd metatarsal head (O'Neill et al. 2023). In the second position (knee extended), participants were prone with a neutral hip and fully extended knee (Liebl et al. 2014). Three attempts were made on each side for both positions and the highest two marks were averaged per side in each position.

Subsequently, a Hans Rudolph metabolic mask and a Garmin HRM Pro heart rate monitor (Garmin HRM-Pro, Garmin Ltd, Olathe, KS, USA) were fitted to participants. In this pilot study breath-by-breath analysis was used to collect metabolic data during treadmill trials (Quark Cart, COSMED, Rome, Italy). Participants were then given a safety briefing and an explanation of the Borg's Rating of Perceived Exertion (RPE) scale (Scherr et al. 2013). Participants then ran a 15-minute warm up on the treadmill at a self-selected pace (repeated for POST) and wore the metabolic mask for the final 5 minutes for familiarization.

Once warmed up, participants ran two 3-minute trials (Hunter et al. 2019) at self-selected goal cross-country race pace (10k pace for the men: 11.55 ± 0.72 km·hr⁻¹; 6k pace for the women: 10.65 ± 0.0 km·hr⁻¹) with 7-10 minutes rest to change shoes and secure shoe markers. During these race pace trials, biomechanical data was collected in each shoe (VP/FL). 3D kinematics and kinetics were recorded during minute 2 of these trials. Subjects did not wear a metabolic mask during race pace trials. Following the race pace trials, motion capture markers were removed and subjects completed four 5-minute trials with 5 minutes rest (Hoogkamer et al. 2018; Healey and Hoogkamer 2022, Joubert and Jones 2022) at a self-selected submaximal pace (RER<1) (Joubert and Jones 2022) while wearing a face mask. Trial paces were kept constant in PRE/POST. Shoe order during testing followed an ABBAAB pattern for all six trials (race pace and submaximal pace) (Joubert and Jones 2022; Jones et al. 2003). Shoe A was randomly selected individually during PRE and kept the same for POST.

2.4 Intervention

Participants were stratified by their RE response to VP during PRE and then randomly assigned to either the VP or FL training group for an 8-week intervention in which they were instructed to complete their hard running workouts and races in their assigned shoe. Easy runs and long runs were done in their standard training shoe of choice. Participants were asked to maintain an 85% adherence rate in their assigned shoe during workouts and races through the 8-week intervention. Importantly, adherence was much lower in the FL-training group and is described in detail in the Results. A weekly questionnaire was completed to record participants' weekly mileage, workout/race details, shoe usage, perceived exertion, and muscular soreness. Perceived muscular soreness was recorded for the day of and the day following a workout/race in the participant's assigned shoe using a five-point Likert scale. RPE was assessed using a 10-point scale (Lea et al. 2022).

2.5 Signal Processing

Metabolic data was collected using breath-by-breath analysis. VO₂ and RER were averaged for the last 3 minutes of the submaximal trials (Hoogkamer et al. 2018). Acute RE benefits of VP compared to FL during the submaximal pace trials in this study are expressed as a % difference in VO₂ when running in VP compared to FL; $(FL-VP)/FL * 100$ (Hoogkamer et al. 2018; Joubert and Jones 2022). We are representing this acute VP performance improvement (VP% Benefit) as a positive value if the runner was more economical in VP and as a negative value if they were less economical in VP compared to FL.

Biomechanics were captured during the race pace trails only. We captured kinematic data at 100 Hz and ground reaction force data at 1000 Hz during minute 2 of the race pace trials (60-120 seconds). Marker trajectories and force plate data were low-pass filtered with a 14 Hz Butterworth filter (Bezodis et al. 2013; Kristianslund et al. 2012). After processing the kinematic data, the latest 10 strides with clean data (i.e. no segments missing, no thigh or shank marker cluster slipping) were exported to Visual 3D for analysis (Visual 3D, C-Motion Inc., Germantown, MD, USA). A 50N vertical GRF threshold was used to determine gait events (footstrike/toe-off). Visual inspection of slow-motion video taken at 240 Hz (iPhone 11 Pro Max, Apple Inc, Cupertino, CA, USA) was used to determine footstrike technique (FST) in VP and FL during PRE and POST. Operational definitions of FST included: rearfoot strike (RFS) - striking with only the posterior third of the foot; forefoot strike (FFS) - striking with only the anterior half of the foot; and midfoot strike (MFS) was used to classify anything in between RFS and FFS (Hasegawa et al. 2007, Hoenig et al. 2020, Meyer et al. 2018).

Visual 3D was used to calculate sagittal plane hip, knee, and ankle joint powers, moments, and angles, along with a metatarsophalangeal (MTP) joint angle, bilaterally using a six degree of freedom model. With a longitudinal study design, joint angles from PRE to POST were prone to small differences in marker placement, therefore joint velocities were calculated using the derivative of the respective joint angle during stance phase.

2.6 Statistical Analysis

We employed an ANCOVA model trying to predict running efficiency as a function of many possible predictor variables, notable among them, assigned training shoe (VP/FL). Due to the small sample size in the pilot study, models were developed using exploration along with stepwise procedures using AIC. In addition, other models are under investigation using other response variables dealing with the aforementioned efficiency.

Effect sizes were determined for differences between shoe intervention groups PRE to POST improvements in RE and changes in VP% Benefit. Hedges *g* was used as a descriptive statistic due to small, uneven group sizes (Hedges 1981). Significance levels calculated with an independent samples Student's *t* test assuming equal variance are given for these variables, as well as VJ, plantarflexor strength, and muscular soreness differences from PRE to POST. *P* values < 0.05 were considered significant. Given the exploratory nature of this pilot study, all trends were described, even when non-significant.

2. Results

On average all participants' RE (VO₂; ml·kg⁻¹·min⁻¹), independent of shoe, improved over the 8-week intervention, though FL-trained runners improved more (5.61±1.11%) than VP-trained runners (0.97 ± 3.64%) (*p*=0.077, effect size (Hedges *g*) =1.409). Looking at the changes in VP% Benefit from PRE to POST, VP-trained runners increased their VP% Benefit (0.21 ± 2.23%) as opposed to FL-trained runners who decreased their VP% Benefit (-0.38 ± 0.24%) (*p* = 0.433, *g* = 0.148), see Table 2. Individual changes in VP% Benefit in both training groups are separated by FST in Figure 2. Breaking down RE by shoe, FL-trained runners improved RE by 5.79 ± 1.02% when running in FL and by 5.43 ± 1.20% when running in VP. VP-trained runners improved RE by 0.84 ± 4.64% when running in FL and by 1.11 ± 2.72% when running in VP.

	FL Training Group (Mean ± SD)		VP Training Group (Mean ± SD)	
	PRE	POST	PRE	POST
Average RE (VO ₂ ; ml·kg ⁻¹ ·min ⁻¹)	52.35 ± 3.23	49.46 ± 4.11	55.18 ± 3.41	54.64 ± 3.96
VP% Benefit	1.55 ± 1.61%	1.17 ± 1.37%	0.67 ± 1.33%	0.88 ± 1.38%

Table 2. Average running economy (RE) (VO₂; ml·kg⁻¹·min⁻¹) and VP% benefit within each intervention shoe group during PRE and POST.

Figure 2. Individual VP% Benefit changes from PRE to POST are shown for each intervention shoe group and runners are classified as having a RFS pattern (solid lines) or non-RFS pattern (dashed lines).

	FL Training Group (Mean ± SD)			VP Training Group (Mean ± SD)		
	PRE	POST	% Diff.	PRE	POST	% Diff.
Vertical Jump (inches)	13.75 ± 3.89	15.75 ± 4.24	14.55%	18.25 ± 5.69	19.16 ± 5.01	4.99%
microFET Knee Flexed (N)	243.3 ± 47.20	346.3 ± 43.64	42.37%	208.7 ± 72.50	279.3 ± 92.78	33.85%
microFET Knee Extended (N)	275.7 ± 44.89	220.5 ± 48.69	- 20.04%	272.1 ± 80.01	260.6 ± 57.21	-4.20%

Table 3. Vertical jump and plantarflexor strength (microFET) values for each training intervention group (VP/FL). The percent difference between PRE and POST, are also reported for each group during PRE and POST.

VJ increased more in FL-trained runners from PRE to POST (14.55%) than VP-trained runners (4.99%) ($p=0.307$). Plantarflexor strength in a knee flexed position increased from PRE to POST by 42.37% in the FL-trained runners, compared to the 33.85% improvement in VP-trained runners ($p=0.234$). In FL-trained runners plantarflexor strength decreased in a knee extended position by 20.04% and the VP-trained runners maintained force production with a small increase of 0.13% in the knee extended position ($p=0.042$), see Table 3. Average perceived muscular soreness was greater in FL-trained runners (3.12 ± 0.64) than VP-trained runners (2.49 ± 0.41) ($p<0.001$) throughout the intervention. In addition, muscular soreness was greater in FL-trained compared to VP-trained runners during both the day of the workout (FL: 3.17 ± 0.70 ; VP: 2.47 ± 0.43 ; $p<0.001$), and the subsequent day (FL: 3.06 ± 0.60 ; VP: 2.50 ± 0.40 ; $p=0.002$). RPE ratings of workouts and races were also higher in FL-trained runners (7.66 ± 1.29) than VP-trained runners (6.57 ± 1.04) ($p=0.007$). See Figure 3 for graphs of perceived muscular soreness and RPE.

A

Figure 3. Perceived muscular soreness and RPE graphs for the 8-week training intervention. **(A)** Average perceived muscular within each intervention training group is noted for both the remainder of the day after intervention workouts and the following day, shown as the point in between intervention workouts. **(B)** Average Borg's RPE (0-10 scale) within each intervention training group is given in relation to represent the perceived effort of each intervention workout.

While participants were initially randomized into training groups, adherence rates between the two groups differed greatly, and some participants switched groups. Given the nature of this small-n pilot study, we opted to keep these participants in the study and describe factors that may have contributed to their adherence choices. The FL-trained group started with five subjects and ended with two, and the VP-trained group started with four subjects and ended with six. One FL-assigned subject dropped out of the study citing intense calf soreness after the first workout. The other two FL-assigned runners self-selected into the VP-training group after the first workout, also citing intense soreness. The VP-training group started with four subjects and ended with six due to this self-selection. The subjects self-selecting into the VP-training group exceeded the requested 85% adherence rate. Soreness and RPE data presented include these three subjects in the FL-trained group for the first workout they completed in FL and then, for the two self-selecting, in the VP-trained group for remaining workouts/races. Upon investigating further, the differences between those who adhered to their assigned shoe and those who did not, we found all FL-assigned subjects that

discontinued training in FL were RFS runners, with only one RFS runner and one FFS runner successfully training in FL over the intervention.

In this pilot study there were no significant correlations between biomechanical and metabolic measures, though non-significant kinematic and kinetic differences were observed when comparing VP-trained runners and FL-trained runners. Due to heterogeneity of footstrike technique among the VP-trained runners and only one non-RFS FL-trained runner having clean kinematic data in PRE, individual subject averages for variables of interest are reported for non-RFS VP-trained (n=2) and FL-trained runners (n=1), see Table 4. From the data presented, small changes seen as potentially notable given the changes in VP% Benefit for the non-RFS VP-trained runners include: decreased peak ankle plantarflexion and dorsiflexion velocities; decreased peak positive ankle power, particularly in VP; increased MTP joint range of motion and dorsiflexion velocity, with MTP joint range of motion increasing more in FL than VP in POST; and an overall decrease in stride rate, particularly in VP. Changes seen in the non-RFS FL-trained runner include: increased peak ankle plantarflexion and dorsiflexion velocities; increased MTP joint range of motion and dorsiflexion velocity, with MTP joint range of motion increasing more in VP than FL in POST; and an increase in stride rate.

				Ankle ROM (degrees)	Peak Ankle Plantarflexion Velocity (degrees·sec ⁻¹)	Peak Ankle Dorsiflexion Velocity (degrees·sec ⁻¹)	Peak Ankle Plantarflexion Moment (Nm·sec ⁻¹)	Peak Ankle Positive Power (W·sec ⁻¹)	MTP Joint ROM (degrees)	Peak MTP Joint Dorsiflexion Velocity (degrees·sec ⁻¹)	Step Rate (steps·min ⁻¹)
				PRE	FL	VP	FL	VP	FL	VP	FL
Non-RFS VP-Trained Runners	SUBJ06	PRE	FL	46.36	1.40	-0.67	5.78	75.20	24.64	-0.67	202.64
			VP	45.69	1.44	-0.54	5.47	64.02	12.79	-0.38	202.89
		POST	FL	35.34	1.15	-0.58	5.59	65.86	29.62	-0.76	203.63
			VP	35.92	1.21	-0.52	5.60	56.94	17.06	-0.47	200.06
	SUBJ07	PRE	FL	45.24	1.42	-0.75	4.63	39.82	18.20	-0.50	191.31
			VP	40.10	1.47	-0.64	4.35	35.72	9.40	-0.25	188.57
		POST	FL	43.99	1.45	-0.72	4.75	43.30	18.75	-0.53	189.94
			VP	37.82	1.46	-0.61	4.26	34.82	9.57	-0.27	187.54
Non-RFS FL-Trained Runner	SUBJ09	PRE	FL	46.33	1.42	-0.74	5.66	60.38	22.31	-0.67	189.83
			VP	43.85	1.47	-0.73	5.05	52.03	12.05	-0.38	186.91
		POST	FL	50.34	1.52	-0.85	5.76	-	23.31	-0.75	191.45
			VP	42.89	1.52	-0.79	5.51	-	13.23	-0.38	187.55

Table 4. Non-RFS VP-trained (SUBJ06 & SUBJ07) and non-RFS FL-trained (SUBJ09) runners' individual data in VP and FL during PRE and POST. Mean values of kinematic, kinetic, and spatiotemporal variables of interest are presented for each subject.

4. Discussion

Due to the small, unbalanced group sizes, low FL-training group adherence, and heterogeneous footstrike characteristics, the findings of this pilot study should be interpreted with caution. We observed a greater improvement in average RE in FL-trained runners compared to VP trained runners, suggesting that training in FL may be more advantageous when trying to optimize RE in training. There are a few potential explanations.

First, it is important to consider that these runners were running in a very structured training environment, with prescribed workout paces and volumes matched between the two training groups. In this specific environment, those FL-trained runners who were able to successfully complete the intervention in FL (2/5), were possibly operating at a higher aerobic output compared to the VP-trained counterparts given the documented acute RE benefits of VP (Hoogkamer et al. 2018; Joubert and Jones 2022; Hébert-Losier et al. 2022), potentially providing greater training stimulus to increase aerobic capacity or RE. There is evidence that higher aerobic workload through speed endurance training can increase RE (Skovgaard et al. 2018), which may explain why less economical footwear worn during speed endurance training could potentially cause an increase in RE. Additionally, Ridge et al. (2015) observed a non-statistically significant increase in RE when traditionally shod runners transitioned to training in minimalist shoes (compared to a control group that also improved RE). The two FL-trained runners also ran on average about 8 miles more per week, which also may have played a role in the observed increase in RE in POST, though there is a lack of evidence directly linking relatively small differences in training volume to changes in RE in trained runners. Skovgaard et al. (2018) showed increases in RE with decreases in volume coupled with increases in speed endurance training, suggesting the closely matched workout volumes between our training groups may have caused similar RE improvements, excluding other factors such as footwear. Relatedly, Ridge et al. (2015) suggested RE improvements observed in runners wearing traditional and minimalist training shoes may be related to improved adherence to training due to being a research study participant, implying training volume may play a role in RE improvements though this is not necessarily related to differences in training volume trained collegiate runners.

Additionally, by training in a shoe that promotes a FFS due to a minimally protective midsole and outsole (Warne et al. 2014; Squadroni et al. 2015), these FL-trained runners may have increased their efficiency by either adopting a FFS rather than RFS or by becoming more efficient in their habitual FFS, though more data is needed to validate transitioning to a FFS improving RE and injury risk (Hamill and Gruber 2017). With only two of five runners being able to train in FL, it seems that any potential benefits of being able to train in FL may only be accessible to those able to tolerate training in the shoe. With only two runners able to successfully train in FL in this pilot study, it is possible that these runners are outliers when considering the general cross-country running population. With that said, we did not give runners directions on how to “break in” the shoes. This lack of a break in period may have contributed to excessive soreness after the first workout. The Nike Victory Waffle XC 5 is also the lightest cross-country racing flat offered by Nike and reduces mass by using a less dense midsole foam and minimally protective outsole. This led to complaints of foot pain when running over gravel surfaces in our FL-trained runners who were able to complete the intervention, and likely made it difficult for the RFS FL-assigned runners to use the shoe for workouts. Using this information, the next phase of the study will use a more protective and cushioned racing flat, and runners will be advised on how to break in the shoe.

The other main finding from this pilot study was that, on average, the VP-trained runners slightly increased their VP% Benefit while FL-trained runners decreased their VP% Benefit. This suggests that by training in VP, VP-trained runners were able to “learn” how to use the shoe more effectively. Further, the non-RFS VP-trained runners improved their acute VP% Benefit to an even greater extent than RFS VP-trained runners. One non-RFS VP-trained runner adopted a RFS when running

in VP during POST while the other non-RFS VP-trained runner had no change in FST in either VP or FL during POST.

By examining biomechanical data from individuals in our pilot study, we propose the following potential explanations for the observed increase in VP% Benefit in the VP-trained runners. We plan to test these explanations more rigorously in future work.

1. First, it is possible runners increased knee and ankle joint stiffness in response to the long-term repeated exposure to cushioning in VP. With acute exposure to cushioning, it is known that individuals improve RE (Worobets et al. 2014; Tung et al. 2014). It has also been shown that runners increase lower extremity stiffness in response to footwear cushioning (Kulmala et al. 2018). With the unique compliance of the polyether block amide (PEBA) foam in VP (Hoogkamer et al. 2018), after repeated exposure over 8-weeks, it seems possible that the VP-trained runners were capable of more optimally/efficiently increasing their knee and ankle joint stiffness, a change that we saw in our pilot study through slower knee and ankle joint velocities when the VP-trained runners were running in VP compared to the FL-trained runners in POST. Alternatively, this increase in joint stiffness could also suggest that the VP-trained runners may have increased reliance on the passive cushioning of the compliant PEBA foam rather than active cushioning during ground contact.
2. In addition, the observed slower ankle plantarflexion velocity in the VP-trained runners may also mean the triceps surae was contracting at a slower velocity. This could provide increased VP% Benefit allowing for more optimal actin-myosin crossbridge formation when in VP (Cigoja et al. 2021).
3. Further, VP-trained runners may learn to use the curved carbon-fiber plate more effectively. They may become more comfortable or effective with the “teeter-totter effect” proposed by Nigg et al. (2020). We saw decreased positive ankle power in VP-trained runners in late stance, which supports this idea. This suggests that runners may increase their ability to take advantage of the carbon plate rather than the energy return of the PEBA foam. The midsole foam seems to return energy earlier in stance than optimal due to its material properties (Matijevich et al. 2022), compared to the plate, which may provide a more optimal timing of energy return through the proposed teeter-totter effect.
4. As a related explanation, runners may increase reliance on the curved carbon-fiber plate to stiffen the MTP joint passively (Hoogkamer et al. 2019), thus decreasing the oxygen utilization associated with actively stiffening the MTP joint. This is supported by the increase in MTP joint dorsiflexion velocity seen in the non-RFS VP-trained runners when running in VP from PRE to POST.
5. Finally, runners may adjust their stride rate when at race pace in response to their training shoe and that stride rate adjustment is applied in every shoe. From our pilot data, runners training in both VP and FL changed their stride rate in the direction of the acute stride rate effects of their training shoe (Joubert and Jones 2022; Hébert-Losier et al. 2022). The FL-trained runner had an increased stride rate when running in both shoes with a greater increase when running in FL, whereas the VP-trained runners generally decreased stride rate in both shoes.

From this pilot study, we infer that the specificity of training principle extends to footwear, where runners become relatively more efficient in the shoe they train in.

4.1 Limitations

Due to the nature of this being a pilot study for an upcoming larger study, it needs to be emphasized that there are many limitations. The small sample size means that individual changes, responses to training, and the myriad of different variables associated with 8-weeks of training as a college student-athlete, could have large influences on the results. Furthermore, with the low adherence in the FL-training group creating unbalanced group sizes, it is difficult to clearly identify trends of statistical or practical significance, particularly when attempting to explain metabolic responses using biomechanics. This is further complicated by limited understanding of what gait characteristics are associated with “responders” and “non-responders” to VP. In this pilot study,

FST was not standardized, which likely prevented between group differences from being observed. A larger sample is needed so runners with different gait characteristics, including FST, can be represented across intervention training shoe groups.

The finding of increased overall RE in the FL-trained runners needs to be considered in the context of the training environment. The participants in this pilot study were all part of the same cross-country program and had the same coach who prescribed workout volume, intensity, and frequency for runners. Runners were put in groups for workouts, and those assigned VP or FL for the intervention were prescribed the same workouts and paces. This means that the VP-trained runners were not able to increase their volume, intensity, or frequency as the acute effects of their training shoe may have allowed (Castellanos-Salamanca et al. 2023; Black et al. 2022). In other training environments with more flexibility, VP-trained runners may be able to increase their workout volume, intensity, or the number of workouts they are able to perform in a week.

The low FL-training group adherence in this pilot study can be attributed to a few factors, some of which we are learning may be future limitations when conducting footwear intervention research in collegiate cross-country athletes. In this pilot study, the Nike Victory Waffle XC 5 racing flat was used as a training shoe for workouts. From this pilot phase, we learned that a more durable and protective racing flat should be used for collegiate cross-country training. Despite some runners assigned to the FL-training group completing their previous season's workouts fully or partially in traditional racing flats, the transition to the FL used in this study was subject to a high attrition rate. This may have been a result of the characteristics of the FL and the surfaces runners were completing workouts on, including gravel and dirt. Additionally, runners were not given specific instructions on how to break in their footwear during workouts, likely causing excessive soreness after the first workout to be the chief complaint of those who discontinued training in FL. The RFS commonality among these runners supports findings by Salzler et al. (2012), though in this population was an unanticipated occurrence due to familiarity with training in traditional racing flats, subject age, training status, and FL only being worn twice a week during the intervention. Care should be taken in future work to appropriately increase training/workout load in novel footwear in this population. In the next phase of this study, a more protective traditional racing flat and a specified method of breaking in prescribed workout shoes will be used to address the adherence issues seen in this pilot study.

Reliability of VJ and calf strength measures presented in this study is either unassessed in this population or in general. VJ test-retest reliability has been assessed in other populations, though not in collegiate distance runners (Nuzzo et al. 2011; Yingling et al. 2018). Runners in this study were not familiar with a maximal countermovement jump prior to participation. The novel microFET positions used in this study were developed using resources available, an isokinetic dynamometer would be a more reliable and valid way to test plantarflexor strength (O'Neill et al. 2023; Marmon et al. 2013). In the knee-flexed position, subjects were seated with their knee and hip in 90 degrees of flexion and their ankle in a neutral position. Their leg was secured and the microFET device was held in place under the second and third metatarsal heads of the foot. In the knee-extended position, subjects were prone with the edge of the table at their tibial tuberosity and their knee extended fully. Subjects steadied themselves and the microFET was placed in the same position under their foot and was secured to the table the subject was on. Test-retest reliability should be established for the microFET positions used before making conclusions about PRE/POST differences between intervention training groups.

Furthermore, there are limitations with the biomechanical analysis of this pilot study. Sagittal plane kinematics and kinetics were the focus of our analysis, though a frontal plane analysis may provide additional information to explain changes in VP% Benefit or overall RE. Frontal plane kinematics and kinetics will be considered in the next phase of this research. Additionally, as we were partially through PRE, we learned how to effectively glue the first and fifth metatarsal head and first toe markers. Unglued markers resulted in missing markers and different placements from PRE-POST, making MTP joint angular velocity the primary outcome measure of interest. The next phase of the

study will exclusively use glued MTP joint and toe markers and will report MTP joint angle, angular velocity, and moment.

Metabolic data was collected with a COSMED Quark metabolic cart using a breath-by-breath analysis, which given the ventilation rate of our subjects has greater error (Beijst et al. 2013). A Parvo Medics True One 2400 (Parvo Medics, Salt Lake City, UT, USA) metabolic cart with a mixing chamber will be used in future work to limit measurement error (Beijst et al. 2013). When looking for PRE to POST differences in footwear specific RE based on training shoe, measurement error and day-to-day variability of RE measurements within-subjects should be considered (Saunders et al. 2004; Blagrove et al. 2017; Shaw et al. 2013). Having a larger sample and greater statistical power will help limit the impact of the aforementioned considerations with group averages more closely representing real changes in shoe specific RE.

4.2 Future Directions

This pilot study is the first longitudinal intervention study to look at the long-term effects of using VP versus FL and has created foundational knowledge as we plan a larger phase-two study. The next phase aims to address many of the limitations of this pilot study and will hopefully provide a clearer picture of the effects of training in VP on performance. In addition to this, we hope to assess changes in biomechanics to gain a deeper understanding of adaptations to training in specific footwear and potentially, if our pilot study trends are supported, uncover what it means to biomechanically “learn” how to use VP. This is an area for future research with a multitude of different study designs besides the one employed here.

Further research needs to be conducted to assess the longitudinal impacts of “super shoes” on performance, injury, and recovery. This pilot study only used the Nike Vaporfly Next% 2 and had VP-trained runners using these shoes only for workouts and races. Looking at the impacts of different brands/models of these “super shoes” on injury, performance, and recovery is needed to increase the generalizability of this type of research. Inclusion of a training group using a more standard training shoe, for example the Nike Pegasus, or a “Tempo” style shoe such as the Nike Tempo Next%, would also give further information about the impact of training in super shoes, though differences would likely be of lesser magnitude than when comparing to a traditional racing flat. Quantifying the recovery benefits of new footwear technologies is an important area of future research that will help inform runners’ footwear choices and provide valuable information to those in the footwear industry who are seeking ways to improve performance, recovery, and reduce injury rates through footwear.

In addition to potential impacts of super shoes on recovery, including perceived muscular soreness as noted in this study, the fatigue delaying characteristics of VP (Castellanos-Salamanca et al. 2023; Black et al. 2022) may increase the workload capacity of runners. This, along with assessing the impact of strategic footwear use in specific workouts, would provide valuable information for coaches and runners seeking to maximize performance.

With PRE and POST data collections each taking three hours per participant, we were not able to include all outcomes of interest. Assessing changes in intrinsic foot muscle strength may give a clearer picture of how long-term use of VP, where the carbon plate acts in parallel with these muscles to stiffen the MTP joint (Hoogkamer et al. 2019), may lead to differences in strength gains compared to non-plated footwear. EMG activation patterns and peaks were not assessed in this pilot study, though will be measured in phase-two. With the high amount of loading during the workouts of this intervention, it would be of interest to look at changes in bone marrow edema between runners using super shoes and a control group, such as the work of Ridge et al. (2013), over a longer period of super shoe use, or before and after prolonged downhill running or marathon completion. Injury data on super shoes is currently limited, with a recent collection of retrospective case studies linking super shoe use and navicular bone stress injuries (Tenforde et al. 2023), highlighting the importance of understanding the risks and benefits associated with transitioning to these shoes. Prospective research assessing the impact of regular super shoe use and injury risk at all ability levels is needed to help inform athletes, coaches, and footwear companies.

Similar to the rise in popularity of using super shoes in workouts in collegiate and elite runners, the habitual use of super shoes in recreational runners has been rising. The benefits and risks associated with this should be assessed. Likewise, the acute and long-term effects of super shoe use for workouts and races in youth athletes needs to be measured. The impact on development, injury risk, and gait biomechanics after maturation should be considered. Is it possible that by using super shoes at a young age, runners become “high responders” to super shoes as they age or change injury rates throughout high school/college?

5. Conclusion

This pilot study suggests a specificity of training effect where participants improved RE more from PRE to POST when running in the shoe type they trained in. Subjects in the FL group, improved RE more than those in the VP group, but those in the VP group increased their acute performance benefit, or “boost,” from VP. These findings would suggest that runners who seek to maximize performance at an elite level should consider completing workouts in flats to improve their RE to a greater extent than if they trained in VP, though using VP periodically or leading up to a race may allow runners to increase their acute VP performance benefit. We plan to test this theory in the second phase of the study to investigate if runners can increase race performance further by periodizing training footwear and integrating greater VP use prior to race day.

The training environment of the runners in this pilot study needs to be taken into consideration. In our study, training loads were matched between groups. The VP-trained runners were not able to increase training volume, intensity, or frequency, though these runners potentially may have been able to increase any of these training variables due to the fatigue delaying characteristics of VP and potential recovery benefits. Additionally, injury susceptibility when training in VP or FL should be considered.

Due to the small, unbalanced group sizes, low FL-training group adherence, and heterogeneous footstrike characteristics, the findings of this pilot study should be interpreted with caution. Only two of five runners were able to train in FL, potentially limiting potential benefits of training in FL to those able to tolerate training in the shoe.

The findings from this study will be tested in with a larger cohort during the next collegiate cross-country season. Further work is needed to test if there are recovery aspects of using VP in training that allow runners to actually train at a higher volume, frequency, or at a higher intensity.

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